

Kinetics and Mechanism of Electron Transfer Reactions in Solutions : Oxidation of Glutamic Acid by Bismuth(V) in Aqueous HClO₄-HF Medium

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Since bismuth(V) in solid salt form is frequently employed as an oxidant in organic syntheses, the solution chemistry of the reagent is not much known. The present study is aimed at probing into the solution chemistry of bismuth(V) in HClO₄-HF medium and studying the reactivity pattern of oxidation of glutamic acid by fluorobismuthate species.

Results and Discussion

¹H nmr spectrum of the hydrazone derivative in DMSO-d₆/CDCl₃ showed presence of carboxylic proton due to a downfield signal at δ11.52, the methylene protons appeared at δ2.16 as singlet, other CH₂ proton peak probably coalesced in DMSO. Methylene proton was exhibited at δ8.17 as triplet. The aromatic protons appeared at δ8.97, 8.37 and 7.97 as doublet, double doublet and doublet with coupling constants 3.1, 3.0 and 3.0 Hz respectively. These results conform to the hydrazone derivative of aldehyde. Therefore, the stoichiometry of the reaction corresponding to these results can be represented as

The kinetic results in brief are as follows. (i) The concentrations of bismuth(V) (1.6–9.8) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and that of glutamic acid (1.0–25.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ were varied keeping other components of the reaction constant. A plot of initial rate (k_i) vs [Bi^V] yielded a straight line passing through the origin, indicating first order with respect to the oxidant. However, the order

with respect to amino acid was complex. (ii) The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying lithium perchlorate concentration and the rate was marginally affected. (iii) The rate decreased with increasing hydrogen ion concentration (Table 1).

Since the rate is not affected by the added F⁻, it is difficult to conclude from the kinetics about the speciation of the fluorobismuth(V) species. Previous authors¹ reported hydroxofluoro species of bismuth(V) (BiF_x(OH)_{6-x}^{-x}) on the premises of the established hydroxyfluoro species of arsenic and antimony respectively. Also, the rate is not affected by HF. The results ascribe to the formation of an ultimate fluoro-species of bismuth(V) (BiF₆⁻). Since the hydrolysis of BiF₆⁻ is slow², it should be slower in presence of the higher hydrogen ion concentrations. Therefore, the BiF₆⁻ concentration in acidic medium should be governed by the equilibrium step (1) particularly in view of the higher fluoride ion affinity towards hydrogen ions. Since the pK's of the glutamic acid ascribe to the cationic species to be the predominantly reactive species, the observed hydrogen ion dependence can not be correlated to glutamic acid. Thus considering the cationic form of the glutamic acid (I) and BiF₆⁻ to be that of bismuth(V), the following mechanism can be envisaged :

TABLE I - HYDROGEN ION VARIATION

[Bi^V] = 1.58 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [III⁺] = 1.5 mol dm⁻³, I = 2.5 mol dm⁻³ (LiClO₄), Temp. = 308 K

[GA] = 0.003 mol dm⁻³ :

[HClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	1.0	1.25	1.5	1.75	2.0	2.25	2.5
k _{expl} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	3.0	—	2.6	—	2.1	—	1.9

[GA] = 0.005 mol dm⁻³ :

k _{expl} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	4.6	4.1	3.9	3.4	3.1	2.8	2.6
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[GA] = 0.010 mol dm⁻³ :

k _{expl} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	6.9	—	5.5	—	4.6	—	4.0
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The loss of bismuth(V) leads to the rate law (5) or (6),

$$-\frac{d[\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}][\text{GA}^+]}{1 + K_p[\text{H}^+] + K[\text{GA}^+]} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or } k' = \frac{kK[\text{GA}^+]}{1 + K_p[\text{H}^+] + K[\text{GA}^+]} \quad (6)$$

where *k'* is an observed pseudo-first order rate constant, [GA⁺] and [Bi^V] are the equilibrium and gross analytical concentrations of glutamic acid and bismuth(V) respectively. Since *K_p* ≥ 10 (due to the hydrogen bonding), the inequality (*K_p*[H⁺] + *K*[GA⁺]) > 1, in the denominator of the rate law (6) is valid. This reduces the rate law (6) to (7),

$$k = \frac{kK[\text{GA}^+]}{K_p[\text{H}^+] + K[\text{GA}^+]} \quad (7)$$

A plot of (*k'*)⁻¹ vs [H⁺]/[GA⁺] from equation (7) was made at different hydrogen ion concentrations that yielded straight line with non-zero intercept. The intercept and slope of the line yielded *K* and *K_p**K*⁻¹ to be (1.66 ± 0.2) × 10⁻² dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ and (19.2 ± 2) × 10⁻² respectively. Similarly, a plot of (*k'*)⁻¹ vs [H⁺]/[GA⁺] was also made at constant [H⁺] that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept. The values of *k* were found to be 1.5 × 10⁻², 1.8 × 10⁻² and 2.85 × 10⁻² dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ and *K_p**K*⁻¹ to be 6.0 × 10⁻², 3.0 × 10⁻² and 1.4 × 10⁻² at 30, 35 and 40° respectively. These

values of *k* derived from two sets of data at 35° are in agreement. However, the values of *K_p**K*⁻¹ derived from the latter plot are slightly higher than that obtained from the plot of (*k'*)⁻¹ vs [H⁺]/[GA⁺]. This, in all probability, is due to scattering of the experimental points in the plot. The energy and entropy of activation for the rate-limiting step calculated in a conventional manner were 135 ± 10 kJ mol⁻¹ and -47 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ at 35° respectively.

Since an intermediate complex is indicated kinetically, this appears to be formed through hydrogen bonding of coordinated fluoride with hydrogen of the α-carboxyl group. Such a complex undergoes intramolecular electron transfer to yield another imine intermediate of transient life time. The latter rapidly undergoes hydrolysis to an aldehyde. The intermediate as envisaged in Scheme 1 via hydrogen bonding orientants in such a manner that decarboxylation occurs in a slow rate limiting step. Since the imine can further interact with bismuth(V), hydrolysis of imine to an aldehyde scores over this oxidation,

where, R = (COOH)(CH₂)₂

Scheme 1

The oxidation of basic (lysine) and acidic (glutamic acid) amino acids containing either $^+\text{NH}_3$ or COOH in the side-chain yields only R-CHO as the product. The α -keto acids have also been reported to be the intermediates or the end-products in the oxidation of a few amino acids^{3,4}. The oxidation of the neutral threonine by bismuth(V) to nitrile is due to the preferential oxidation to hydrolysis of imine. Nevertheless, if Pokrouskaya⁶ views of relative reactivities of the amino acids in acidic medium are considered, the facile oxidation of lysine as compared to glutamic acid is in accord to this view.

Experimental

Sodium bismuthate (A.R., Riedel) was used as a source of bismuth(V). Bismuth(III) was obtained from Bi_2O_3 (AnalaR). Hydrofluoric and perchloric acids (A.R., Riedel) were used. Teflon vessels were employed for storing the solutions of bismuth(V). All other chemicals were either of AnalaR or G.R. (Merck) grade and were used as such. Double-distilled water was employed throughout. A transparent solution¹ of bismuth(V) was obtained after stirring sodium bismuthate in a mixture of HCl_4 (1.0 mol dm^{-3}) and HF (1.5 mol dm^{-3}) for 15 min. The solution was standardised iodometrically. However, fresh solutions of bismuth(V) were prepared when required. Bismuth(V) solutions were free from hydrogen peroxide but contained large quantities of bismuth(III), the latter being an impurity in bismuthate sample.

Our repeated attempts to prepare bismuth(V) solution in HClO_4 as reported earlier⁴ were not successful. A suspension of bismuth(V) instead of a solution always resulted leading to the disappearance of bismuth(V) after a few minutes.

Kinetic procedure : The measured quantities of Bi^{V} and other reaction components were mixed in teflon flasks immersed in a thermostated water-bath ($35 \pm$

0.1°). The reaction was initiated by adding the pre-equilibrated solution of the glutaric acid (GA). An aliquot (5 or 10 cm^3) was withdrawn periodically for the iodometric analysis of the remaining oxidant.

Initial rates (k_1) were computed employing plane mirror method⁷. Pseudo-first order plots were made wherever the substrate concentration was 10-fold the concentration of the oxidant. Second order plots were also made wherever reaction conditions permitted. Triplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 5\%$.

The reactions were carried out taking excess (GA) over Bi^{V} in a thermostated water-bath for 4 h. The reaction mixtures were concentrated after ensuring completion iodometrically. 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine solution was added to the reaction mixture and then left overnight at $\sim 5^\circ$. The resulting orange-yellow solid was washed with ice-cold HCl (2 mol dm^{-3}) and dried to yield the hydrazone derivative.

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